

Expectations for Conduct of Systematic Reviews in Chemical Risk Assessment (ECoSys-CRA): an interim code of practice

Discussion draft.

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"Readers often find that research reports fail to provide a clear and transparent account of the methods and adequate reporting of the results. If authors do not provide sufficient details of the conduct of their study, readers are left with an incomplete picture of what was done and found. Poorly reported research may result in misinterpretation and inappropriate application in clinical settings. New research projects may also be based on misleading evidence from poorly reported studies. As such, funds devoted to support research may not be used optimally." (Moher et al. 2014b)

"Suboptimal systematic reviews and meta-analyses can be harmful given the major prestige and influence these types of studies have acquired." (Ioannidis 2016)

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31 **Context: What role could formal standards play in improving systematic reviews?**

32 *Quality management and standards: a brief introduction*

33 Quality management consists of two interplaying processes of quality assurance and quality
34 control. Quality assurance is the process for preventing mistakes or defects in the production of
35 goods and their delivery to users; quality control specifically refers to the testing of products to
36 uncover potential defects, with reporting mechanisms back to management to allow or deny
37 product release (Manghani 2011).

38 Standards are a set of agreed principles or criteria for a product, service or practice, such
39 that users of those products can make reliable assumptions about their performance, safety,
40 compatibility and/or other features as specified in the standard (British Standards Institution
41 2016b). Standards vary in detail and prescriptiveness according to the function they perform,
42 from "specifications" which set out detailed, absolute requirements, to flexible "codes of
43 practice" which recommend "sound and good practice as currently undertaken by competent
44 and conscientious practitioners" (British Standards Institution 2016a).

45 Standards can contribute to both quality assurance and quality control: insofar as they
46 describe practices which help ensure a product, service or practice is fit for purpose they offer
47 guidance which can be expected to ensure a minimum level of quality is reached; when
48 describing product performance, they can provide a set of quality benchmarks against which a
49 product can be tested.¹

50 *The need for better quality management in systematic review*

51 Quality management processes in academic publishing should ensure that only fit-for-
52 purpose systematic reviews get published. In the broad context of quality assurance, "fit for
53 purpose" means a product should be suitable for the intended purpose. In the specific context of
54 systematic review, it means that SRs should be truthful (i.e. minimise risk of bias² in their
55 results and conclusions); they should ask an important question; and they should include all the

¹ We can think about illustrating the QM/QA/QC discussion with examples from analytical chemistry, laboratory assays and GLP standards, to bring home how this might apply in the context of conducting and publishing fit-for-purpose SRs and secondary research.

² In our paper from our previous workshop (Whaley et al. 2016a) we described risk of bias in SRs as coming from three sources: "bias in the conduct of a review (e.g. because of inappropriate methods for identifying and selecting evidence for inclusion in the review); bias because the material available for the review is not representative of the evidence base as a whole (due to selective publication); and bias arising from flaws in the design, conduct, analysis and reporting of individual studies included in the review that can cause the effect of an intervention or exposure to be systematically under- or over-estimated".

56 information about methods and results such that a reader can judge the relevance and validity
57 of their results and use their findings.

58 While quality management is fundamental to ensuring only high-quality systematic reviews
59 (SRs) get published, the processes which researchers follow in planning, conducting and
60 reporting SRs, and journals follow in deciding which SR manuscripts are worth publishing,
61 receive inconsistent attention, and there is evidence that the largely informal approaches to
62 quality assurance employed by journals are resulting in large numbers of low-quality systematic
63 reviews being published. For example, Moher and colleagues estimated the number of
64 stringently defined systematic reviews published in 2004 as approximately 2500, yet the
65 PubMed search for the tag for "systematic review" yielded 8989 items for the same year (Moher
66 et al. 2007). Ioannidis recently described the production of medical systematic reviews and
67 meta-analyses as having reached "epidemic proportions" but estimates that only about 3% of
68 manuscripts are "decent and clinically useful" (Ioannidis 2016).³

69 There is very little research into the quality of systematic reviews being published in the
70 environmental health field. A screening of the literature by three of the authors (PW, GP, CH)
71 shows inconsistent understanding of minimum reporting requirements for systematic reviews
72 published in environmental health journals (Figure 1). The number of purported SRs published
73 without protocols, which did not explicitly consider the generalisability of the evidence base, or
74 which did not formally assess the internal validity of included evidence is cause for concern.⁴

75 Few environmental health journals appear to formally endorse any kind of publication
76 standard for systematic reviews: only three of the journals which had published environmental
77 health SRs at the time of the literature screening had either endorsed the PRISMA standard or
78 recommended that authors follow it. At time of writing, only two dedicated environmental
79 health journals seem to have formally endorsed PRISMA, and only one environmental health
80 journal has an editor for systematic reviews (Whaley et al. 2016b).

81 The conclusion is that peer-review and current quality assurance practices by researchers
82 and at journals, as they relate to ensuring proper conduct, reporting and publication of
83 systematic reviews, are failing badly in medicine and could well be failing in environmental
84 health.

³ Participants with a particular interest in Day 1 proceedings will likely be struck by how many SRs are considered by Ioannidis to be doomed from the outset, by asking questions of too little research value.

⁴ Note that this screening did not investigate the validity of methods used, only whether information was provided which might allow validity of methods to be determined.

85 **A standard for systematic reviews in chemical risk research**

86 *The existing standards landscape*

87 Standards for reporting and conduct of medical research have proliferated in the last two
88 decades, with the EQUATOR Network's online Library for Health Research Reporting currently
89 listing over 200 reporting guidelines. Although many of these guidelines are concerned with
90 reporting of primary research, there are a number of guidelines for reporting of systematic
91 reviews, such as the PRISMA checklist for systematic reviews of interventions (Moher et al.
92 2009) and the MOOSE reporting guidelines for systematic reviews of observational studies in
93 medicine (Stroup et al. 2000). Guidelines which focus explicitly on conduct are much fewer but
94 include the What Works in Health Care standards for systematic reviews (Eden et al. 2011) and
95 the Cochrane Editorial Unit's "MECIR" expectations for conduct of systematic reviews of
96 interventions (Chandler et al. 2013).

97 While in the environmental health and chemical risk assessment disciplines there is some
98 published research into e.g. the key elements for judging the quality of a risk assessment
99 (Fenner-Crisp, Dellarco 2016) which can be interpreted as a guideline for conduct, and there are
100 also surveys of weight-of-evidence guidelines (Rhomberg et al. 2013; Agerstrand, Beronius
101 2016), there appear to be no formal standards for conduct of systematic reviews developed
102 specifically for chemical risk assessment or its components. Given the potential value of a
103 standard for conduct of systematic reviews in the chemical risk assessment disciplines, we
104 believe one ought to be developed.⁵

105 *The objectives of the ECoSys-CRA Standard*

106 We are interested in developing a standard focusing explicitly on best practices in
107 conducting SRs in CRA, deliberately going beyond encouraging the "constructive unease"
108 generated by reporting standards (Schulz et al. 2014) which only indirectly guides authors in
109 selecting methods for conducting SRs. ECoSys-CRA should describe a minimum set of

⁵ Considered as an intervention, there is actually limited evidence of efficacy of guidelines on their own. There is some evidence that journals which endorse the CONSORT statement publish better-reporting clinical trials than those which do not, though the effect is modest (Altman, Simera 2014); however, a recent systematic review suggests limited to no efficacy of endorsement of standards as an intervention to improve the quality of published manuscripts (Page et al. 2016). Given the lack of systematic efforts to enforce standards, it is perhaps not surprising there is limited evidence of efficacy; furthermore, a minimum standard as a reference point against which to judge the quality of conduct of a systematic review is unlikely to be harmful. It should also be noted that improving publishing standards will require a complex intervention of which a standard is only part, though likely fundamental to distinguishing good practices from inadequate ones.

110 procedures for planning and conduct of a systematic review, such that if followed by a group of
111 authors, would yield a SR which is fit for purpose.

112 Our other motive for proposing the standard is to bring into the open the disagreements and
113 differing perceptions of what ought to be done in an SR, as are evidenced by the different
114 approaches in the literature, as a first step in developing consensus among SR practitioners in
115 the CRA disciplines of what needs to be done in order for a SR to be fit for purpose.

116 *Methods for developing the ECoSys-CRA standard*

117 High-quality, robust standards are typically based on three things: (a) *expectation* that the
118 practices described in the standard contribute to being fit for purpose; (b) *hard evidence* that
119 the practices contribute to fitness for purpose; and (c) *broad acceptance* of the practices among
120 the practicing community. Standards should also be accompanied by an elucidation document
121 which explains to the user the reasoning behind the inclusion of each clause in the standard.

122 These three components imply a certain process for developing a standard: (1) a systematic
123 review of existing standards and guidelines to determine the need for a new standard; (2) a
124 systematic review of the prevalence of current research practices; (3) critical appraisal of those
125 practices for completeness, and face and construct validity; (4) a process to determine
126 consensus on best practices and detailing the criteria for the standard.

127 Moher and colleagues recommend a four-step framework to accommodate these
128 requirements, prior to activities to promote implementation of a standard (Moher et al. 2014a).
129 We describe steps 1-4 as being the foundations on which the "three pillars" A-C of a robust
130 standard are built (Figure 2).

131 These foundations and pillars of the ideal process put some restrictions on what we can
132 realistically achieve at our workshop. While we arguably have good collective understanding of
133 (a) for many of the steps of CRA, we have little of (b). Developing (b) via (1), (2) and (3) requires
134 capacity not yet available to us. While we may be able to agree among ourselves for (c), the
135 engagement and review processes we need to conduct to secure sufficiently broad consensus
136 that we can describe ourselves as speaking for the SR community as a whole, are also beyond
137 our reach at this immediate juncture.

138 While it would therefore be a misnomer to describe the outcome of our workshop as a
139 "standard", it is accepted that standardisation is a process which can begin with the articulation
140 of a general set of recommendations ("code of practice"), in lieu of resourcing the more rigorous

141 research and consensus-building processes which lead to formal standards.⁶ We can therefore
142 legitimately make a start with a placeholder standard in lieu of acquiring time and resource to
143 conduct steps 1-4. Our outcome from the workshop will therefore be akin to a "code of practice".

144 **Workshop plan**

145 *Objective / targeted outcome*

146 Review each of the criteria in the draft ECoSys-CRA standard (see Excel table) for conduct of
147 systematic reviews in chemical risk assessment and its related fields, aiming to achieve
148 consensus on (a) which of the proposed criteria should be included, (b) how those criteria
149 should be formulated, and (c) whether there are any additional criteria which should be
150 included, and if so how they should be formulated. The outcome is a "code of practice" for
151 conduct of SRs in the CRA disciplines.

152 *Specific considerations for discussion*

- 153 » For the purposes of discussion, we are **assuming that a systematic review is conducted**
154 **in eight steps**: planning the SR; searching for evidence; selecting evidence for review;
155 extracting data; appraisal of the validity of the evidence; synthesising the evidence;
156 interpreting the evidence and summarising what it means for the review question; drawing
157 conclusions (see Figure 3).
- 158 » Fundamental to standards is lack of ambiguity. Some guidelines require authors to e.g.
159 "protect independence of the review team" but this is not adequate because it is ambiguous
160 as to what level of protection is required, and therefore it cannot be determined when it has
161 been achieved. In fact, protecting the independence of the review team is an objective; the
162 purpose of a standard is to give guidance on how to achieve this. We should focus on
163 articulating, as far as possible, **unambiguous standards** for conducting systematic reviews,
164 bearing in mind that some judgement calls in the SR process resist unambiguous
165 categorisation (e.g. decisions on whether data is too heterogeneous to permit meta-
166 analysis).

⁶ It is probably somewhat misleading for many existing guidelines to be called standards: while they might articulate a set of requirements, few are the outcome of an authentic standardisation process.

- 167 » Chemical risk assessment consists of **a number of sub-disciplines**, for which a range of SRs
168 with different objectives and relevant types of evidence could be conducted. How much do
169 we want to anticipate this in detailing our ECoSys-CRA standard?
- 170 » At this stage, the standard makes **no specific mention of quality control measures** at
171 point of internal review, peer-review or publication which would prevent reviews which are
172 not fit for purpose from being published. These should be discussed (see Figure 4).
- 173 » ISO and BSI standards stipulate **levels of requirement** for each clause in a standards
174 document: "shall" (required, not optional); "should" (recommended but optional); "may"
175 (permission to do); "can" (possibility or capability). Can we identify what actors "shall" and
176 "should" do at this stage, or should we stick with a broad set of recommendations and leave
177 deciding which are compulsory until a later stage in the process?
- 178 » While we have good detail on appraising limitations in design and conduct of included
179 studies, there is no **guidance on assessing the generalisability of included studies**.
180 Should this be a distinct step in the SR methodology for CRAs, and if so, how should it be
181 conducted? (In medical SRs, it is only considered across the evidence base as a whole, but in
182 CRA it seems a more fundamental component with a higher risk of biased interpretation.)

183 *Note on consensus approaches*

184 Consensus is defined by ISO as: "general agreement, characterized by the absence of
185 sustained opposition to substantial issues by any important part of the concerned interests and
186 by a process that involves seeking to take into account the views of all parties concerned and to
187 reconcile any conflicting arguments." [ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, definition 1.7]

188 We will be following a consensus approach in determining the ECoSys-CRA criteria. This is
189 the normal method used for defining standards and codes of practice at BSI and ISO level.
190 Participants should note this may feel like a "race to the bottom" process for establishing a
191 minimum set of criteria which ensure a product is fit for purpose, understood as a body of
192 requirements which a skilled group of practitioners would not necessarily see as capturing best
193 possible practice, but can live with as being good enough (i.e. a necessary tolerable minimum).

194 The purpose of defining the standard in this way is to produce a document of public record of
195 minimum requirements for best practice which can be referred to, critiqued and improved over
196 time. There will be some present who are highly committed to conflicting approaches in
197 conducting a systematic review. In these circumstances, discussion should not become bogged
198 down in the relative merits of these approaches, but try to capture consensus on what it is in

199 these approaches which can be expected to yield SRs which are fit for purpose, i.e. are truthful,
200 useful, and contain enough information to judge relevance and validity (we are interested in
201 what the standard ought to be, not how the standard might be met). Participants should aim for
202 as high a standard as possible (opposition to a criterion ought always to be relevant and
203 reasoned) but be aware that the desired outcome is a functional standard to which everyone
204 can agree to adhere.

205 We do not expect to secure consensus on the day. In the event that consensus cannot be
206 reached in a reasonable amount of time, the issues will be recorded and parked for resolution at
207 a future date. We expect to organise teleconferences and email discussions in the coming weeks
208 to identify and resolve contentious issues.

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Figures

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Paper							7. Confidence in Evidence					9. Declarations		
	Objective	Protocol	Search	Selection	Validity Assessment	Synthesis	Internal Validity	Directness	Consistency	Precision	Publication Bias	Conclusions	Author Interests	Author Contributions
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7.1	7.2	7.3	7.4	7.5	8	9.1	9.2
Willhite et al. (2014)	C	C	C	C	A	C	C	A	C	C	C	C	A	C
Javed et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	C	C	A	C	C	C	C	C	A	C
Jaacks et al. (2015)	A	C	A	A	C	C	A	C	C	A	C	C	A	C
Lu et al. (2015)	A	C	A	A	C	A	C	C	C	C	A	A	A	C
Hamra et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	C	A	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C
LaKind et al. (2014)	C	C	A	A	A	A	A	C	A	C	C	A	A	C
Shin et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	C	A	C	C	A	A	A	A	A	C
Song et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	C	C	A	A	C	A	C	A	A	C
Pineles et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C
Bell et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	C	A	C	A	C
Boffetta et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C	A	A	C
Goodman et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C	A	C	A	A	A	C
Goodman et al. (2015)	A	C	A	A	C	A	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C
Janghorbani et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C	A	C	A	A	A	C
Rota et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	C	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	A	C
Vawda et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C	A	A	A	C	A	C
Vlaanderen et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	C	A	A	A	A	C	A	A	A	C
Wang et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	C	A	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C
Ashworth et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C
Boothe et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	C
Pearson et al. (2015)	C	C	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	C
Bach et al. (2015)	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	C	A	A	A
Johnson et al. (2014)	A	C	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	C
Kousta et al. (2014)	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	C

Key	
A	Information relevant to appraisal of domain is reported
C	No information relevant to appraisal of domain is reported

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Figure 1: Reporting of methods used in systematic reviews published in the top 20 environmental health journals between January 2014 and June 2015, as ranked by impact factor. See supplemental information for questionnaire and domain clarification, search and selection methods etc.

Figure 2: The foundations and “three pillars” of the standardisation process, whereby robust standards are founded on knowledge and critical appraisal of current practices, and consensus on what best practice would be, to generate acceptance for a standardised approach, and evidence and expectation that the standardised approach will be effective in generating fit-for-purpose systematic reviews.

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Figure 3: The steps of a conducting a SR, as assumed by the ECoSys-CRA framework

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Figure 4: The steps of conducting, reporting and publishing a systematic review, for consideration of opportunities for quality control interventions.

223 **Publication bibliography**

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